

ABSTRACT

Background and aims: Few studies have prospectively evaluated predictors of mortality in nonagenarian cohorts. Our objective was to determine a set of predictors of all-cause mortality in a cohort of nonagenarians after one year of follow-up.

Methods: 186 nonagenarians were evaluated prospectively, 137 of whom lived in their own homes (74%) and 49 (26%) were institutionalized. Functional status was determined by the Lawton-Brody (LI) and Barthel Index (BI), and cognition by the Spanish version of the Mini Mental State Examination (MEC). The Charlson score was used to measure global comorbidity. Nutritional status was evaluated by the short version of the Mini Nutritional Assessment questionnaire (short- MNA).

Results: The sample was composed of 143 women (76.5%) and 43 men, with a mean age of 93.06 (3.1) years. The rate of mortality was 19.3%. There were no differences in mortality between men and women. Although the BI and LI were both related to 1-year mortality in bivariate, unadjusted analysis, their contribution was minimal in multivariate analyses. Age, heart failure and short-MNA remained associated with mortality in the multivariate analyses.

Conclusions: This study supported the importance of age, heart failure and nutritional status in predicting 1- year mortality in nonagenarians.